

A LOOK AT THE WORK OF JOHN STEINBECK.

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Abstract: This article presents a scientific and theoretical reflection on the work of John Steinbeck, a major representative of English literature.

Keywords: The Golden Cup, The Grapes of Wrath, Tortilla Flat, man, good, evil, struggle, image, English literature, The Moon is Down, etc.

In our country, the promotion of a culture of tolerance, strengthening mutual understanding and solidarity between nations and confessions, and educating the younger generation on this basis are priorities of state policy. From this perspective, the work of John Steinbeck, a major representative of English literature, is of particular importance.

John Steinbeck (1902–1968) was an American writer who deeply described the human psyche, social injustice, and the lives of ordinary people through his works. His work covers various genres such as novels, short stories, short stories, and essays. The following is a list of Steinbeck's major works: His major epic novels: *The Goblet of Gold* (1929): This historical novel is based on the life of 17th-century pirate Henry Morgan, and describes his adventures and inner feelings. *To an Unknown God* (1933): Four brothers move to California to work on a farm. When a drought destroys their crops, they face various challenges. *Tortilla Flat* (1935): The story of a group of Spanish-speaking paisanos in Monterey and their struggles with friendship, loyalty, and life's challenges. *A Doubtful Battle* (1936): A labor activist fights to organize California fruit pickers. *The Grapes of Wrath* (1939): A poor immigrant family from Oklahoma seeks a new life in California. This novel won Steinbeck the Pulitzer Prize in 1940. *"Cannery Row"* (1945): The story of a disastrous party thrown by a small-town Californian friend for Doc. *"East of Eden"* (1952): The story of two families living in the Salinas Valley depicts the human struggle between good and evil. *"Winter's Worry"* (1961): The story of a man living on Long Island's inner struggles and moral choices after his family loses their social status. John Steinbeck was also a prolific writer in the short story genre. His *"Of Mice and Men"* (1937): Two migrant workers seek work in California during the Great Depression. Their friendship and dreams are tested. *"Red Pony"* (1937): A story of growth and maturity through the relationship between a boy and his pony on a California ranch. *"Moonlight"* (1942): A story of the aftermath of a small coastal town in Northern Europe being invaded by an unknown army. *"The Pearl"* (1947): A poor fisherman finds a huge pearl that brings disaster, not

happiness, to his family. "The Long Valley" (1938): A collection of 12 short stories set in the Salinas Valley. "The Red Pony Stories" (1937): Contains episodic stories about a boy and his life on a California ranch..

The author also has non-fiction works; "The Russian Journal" (1948): A narrative work in the form of a report on Steinbeck's travels through the Soviet Union under Joseph Stalin. "Journal from the Sea of Cortez" (1951): Steinbeck's personal journal of a six-week expedition with marine biologist Ed Ricketts in the Gulf of California.

John Steinbeck's works are distinguished by their deep analysis of the human psyche, their critical approach to social injustice, and their truthful depiction of the lives of ordinary people. His work occupies an important place not only in American, but also in world literature.

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